

Research

Autism and Bilingualism: Exploring Pakistani Parents' Perceptions and Experiences of Raising Bilingual Children with Autism

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Abstract: Autism spectrum disorder is a neurological disorder which makes communication and social interaction hard for the people diagnosed with ASD. The most common symptom of ASD is language delay, many practitioners, educators and parents believe that exposing children with ASD to multiple languages may cause confusion for them. This study investigates the perceptions and experiences of parents with regard to linguistics choices that they make. This study utilizes a qualitative method. Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis is used as a method and data analysis is also guided by the method of IPA. The results from this study shows that value of bilingualism in culture maintenance, socialization skills and development of cognitive skills are major factors behind the maintenance of bilingualism by parents with autistic children. Despite there being challenges in language learning, parents with autistic children are making conscious efforts in maintaining bilingualism.

Keywords: Autism, Bilingualism, IPA, Language maintenance, ASD, Language Choices, Parental decisions.

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Introduction

In multilingual context parents are often faced with making conscious decisions about maintaining a particular language or avoiding one. In contexts where a power language exists, such as: English, then the power language is more likely to be maintained instead of native languages. Such decisions are further complicated in the situations where a child is identified with a neurological disorder, one such developmental disorder is "Autism Syndrome Disorder" or 'ASD' (Howard, Gibson, Katsos, 2021). Individuals who are on the autism spectrum have communication difficulties, they acquire language much late than other typically developing children. This aspect of ASD lead parents and even many health experts to believe that exposure to more than one language may cause confusion for children with autism. However, a vast amount of previous research has proved that bilingualism or multilingualism is not harmful for children on the spectrum, nor is it proved to be beneficial for the autistic children. It does not have any detrimental effect on children's developmental (Prevost & Tuller, 2022).

The aim of this study is to explore parental perceptions about the maintenance of two or more languages with their children who are currently diagnosed with Autism and exploring the experiences of raising autistic children in a highly multilingual society such as Pakistan.

Background of the Study

Most of the research about autism and bilingualism is done in contexts where English is the first or second language. Previous research on this topic is focused on immigrants and first or second generation of immigrants, their exposure is limited to two or three languages. The current study presents an interesting case because Pakistan is a very linguistically diverse country, there are around 72 languages spoken in Pakistan. Five major languages of Pakistan are: Punjabi, Sindhi, Pashto, Balochi and Urdu, other than these languages there are many local languages that are spoken as first language by their speakers. Urdu is mother tongue of only 8% of Pakistani population but it is widely understood and spoken in the country. English has the status of being official language of Pakistan, it is used in the domains of education, bureaucracy, judiciary and media. (Rahman, 2008). Speaking English is believed to provide career growth opportunities and social mobility. Due to this reason, parents make great efforts to teach their children English language. According to Pakistan Autism Society (2021): there are around 400,000 children currently diagnosed with ASD in Pakistan. Such children face many social stigmas, they are believed to have limited abilities. Due to this reason, the decision to expose them to multiple language is also affected. This study investigates the parental decisions about maintaining multilingualism in children with autism disorder.

Research Questions:

1. What are the parents' views about the value of multilingualism who are currently raising a child on autism spectrum?
2. What are parents' experiences of raising a child with ASD in a multilingual family setting?

Research Objectives:

1. To explore the parents' views about the value of multilingualism who are currently raising a child on autism spectrum.
2. To explore parents' experiences of raising a child with ASD in a multilingual family setting.

Literature Review

Research has documented that the families with children with autism spectrum disorder are advised to avoid the use of multiple languages (Hampton et al, 2017). These advices are not consistent with the growing body of research about autism and multilingualism, evidence from recent research shows that children with ASD are completely capable of being multilingual. (McDermott et al. 2013) In fact, there is no evidence that bilingual maintenance has adverse effects on the social, cognitive, and linguistic development of children with autism. Multilingual autistic children perform similarly as their typically developing peers. (Dai et al, 2018).

According to Wu & Zhang (2022) bilingual acquisition in autistic children is unique, therefore, the parents of autistic children must have different experiences of raising bilingual autistic children than neuro-typical children. The challenges faced by parents of bilingual autistic children extend not only to language selection, but also to differing opinions from practitioners on the impact of language selection on the development of children with autism. Existing literature on this topic suggests that parents are dissuaded by professionals and educators to maintain their native language. Mostly for the reason of avoiding further language delay. (Bird et al, 2016). However, the suggestion for

monolingual approach is deemed very problematic because it can isolate a child from their community. Furthermore, if parents are not fluent in second language, they might have difficulty in teaching it to their children. (Bird et al, 2016).

Related Studies

To better understand the topic of the research, some related studies have been reviewed. There are some studies about parental perceptions and language choices among parents with a child on autism spectrum. Yu (2013) explored language practices of 10 bilingual Chinese/English speaking immigrants with children on ASD, the results revealed that the parents valued their native language but they were reluctant in exposing it to their children.

Ijalba (2016) conducted a qualitative study to understand the experiences of raising a child with autism in Hispanic immigrant families. This study investigated how bilingualism influence the language choices of parents. It was revealed in the results that the mothers were hesitant speaking Spanish with their children. Themes of social isolation and stigmatization also emerged from the data.

Howard et al (2021) investigated parental perceptions about maintaining bilingualism in children with autism, this study was conducted in UK. A comparison between the perceptions of monolingual English speaking families and bilingual Welsh/English speaking families was drawn. The study revealed that parents have positive perceptions about maintaining bilingualism but their practices are not consistent with their beliefs.

Sher, Gibson, & Browne (2021) explored perspectives and experiences of parents and practitioners on Hebrew-English bilingualism for autistic children. The results of this study showed that both practitioners and parents felt that having to adopt a monolingual approach was unjust, in line with conceptions of forced monolingualism.

The above studies on autism and maintenance of bilingualism are conducted in contexts where families have to choose between English and their native language. Most studies on this topics investigate immigrant parents' perceptions. No studies are conducted in more linguistically diverse contexts like Pakistan where children of minority language groups have to learn at least 3 and sometimes 4 languages. Such contexts might further complicate the parental choices about maintaining multilingualism in children with ASD.

Research Methodology

Considering the nature of the study, a qualitative methodology has been utilized to better understand the perceptions and experiences of the parents currently raising a child with Autism. Qualitative research allows the researcher to capture the complex realities of human experience and helps them to understand a social phenomenon in deep (Denzin & Lincoln, 2008). Within the qualitative approach, Interpretative phenomenological analysis has been used both as an overarching framework and a method to guide this study. Interpretative phenomenological analysis has three guiding principles: it is idiographic, inductive and interrogative. It is idiographic because it moves away from a single case study to look for patterns among a number of participants (Smith et al., 2017) it is inductive because it is data-driven rather than theory driven (Shaw, 2010) and it is interrogative because it connects the data to existing literature. IPA is a useful method in autism research because it aims to give a voice to minority groups of the society.

Data Sampling

Purposive sampling was used for this study, participants were selected on the basis of the researcher's judgement, and they were representative of the population under investigation. The participants were selected having a broad array of perspectives.

Data Analysis

The data was analyzed using Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis developed by Smith and colleagues (2009). IPA has seven stages for data analysis:

1. Reading and re-reading the transcripts carefully
2. Noting down the descriptive comments in the left hand margin.
3. Noting down the emergent themes in right hand margin.
4. Search for connections throughout the themes.
5. Repeat the first four stages for all the transcripts.
6. Identifying superordinate themes across all accounts.

Emergent Themes

Theme 1: Perceptions about the value of bilingualism

All the parents showed positive attitude towards bilingualism, they reported that bilingualism could have a positive influence on their child with autism. Parents reported that it may help the child to develop communication skills, it may help the child with cognition development and maintaining bilingualism would transfer the cultural values from one generation to another.

(A) Impact on Communication

Parents report that teaching more than one language would provide more opportunities for their children to take part in communication with different people. It would help them to open up more and it would also teach them communication skills such as perspective-taking as they would consider the language preferences of other people.

(B) Impact on Cognition

Parents indicated that bilingualism might aid in cognition development. Learning and using more than one language would result in cognitive flexibility. However, there is no evidence that supports this claim that bilingualism would have cognitive advantages for autistic children but parents' believe that it would have a positive impact on their child's cognition.

(C) Transfer of Culture

Culture is a very important element of Pakistani society, parents reported that they want to maintain bilingualism so the children could learn their cultural values. Some unique features of culture and experiences could not be translated into another language, therefore, maintaining home language is important to maintain cultural values.

Theme 2: Factors impacting Language maintenance

All the parents that participated in this study had to make difficult language decisions, however the common factors that influenced their language choices are: parents' own linguistic profile, communication with family and the role of English in Pakistani society.

(A) Communication with Family

All the parents that participated in this study expressed that bilingualism is important for them because they would like their children to be able to communicate with their elders and extended relatives. It is more of a necessity than a

choice for them because they have to depend on their family for so many things, therefore, they need to speak with their extended relatives and community in the local or home language.

(B) Role of English in Pakistani Society

Participants indicated that English language is important in Pakistani society, they themselves had to face some difficulties while learning this language but it was necessary to learn. English is a requirement for jobs and it is also the medium of instruction in higher education. Due to this reason, the parents want to teach English along with their own home language to their children with autism.

Conclusion

Autism Spectrum Disorder is characterized by speech delay, hence many parents believe that teaching more than one language may confuse children with ASD. The current research reveals that Pakistani parents have positive perceptions about maintaining bilingualism and their views about bilingualism are also consistent with their language practices. Despite there being challenges in language learning, parents with autistic children are making conscious efforts in maintaining bilingualism. These language decisions are based on complex experiences of parents raising children in a multilingual society, factors such as family well-being, role of the dominant language and advice received from the practitioners influence these decisions.

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